

remained submerged for 6 d in water up to a maximum depth of 150 cm.

We scored submergence tolerance on a 1-9 scale 5 d after the flood receded. Some degree of submergence tolerance (score 1-5) was recorded in 75% of the cultivars (Table 1). This percentage of submergence tolerance is more than 10 times more than the percentage of varieties showing submergence tolerance from 18,256 entries screened at IRRI. This greater submergence tolerance may be due to the greater frequency of flooding in Cambodia and the natural selection for submergence tolerance occurring in farmers' fields.

The severity of submergence used here was similar to that in tests of the International Rice Germplasm Center (IRGC) as scored in two common cultivars; Srau Timor (score 5 on both tests) and Srau Thougon (score 7 on our test and score 9 in IRGC tests). A submergence score of 1 was recorded for entries from 5 of 13 provinces (Table 2).

Submergence score of 3, however, was recorded for these entries from nine provinces: Bak Changkes, Damnoeub Krape, Khmao Kdet, Khnang Khmaing, Kho, Kmean Chmous, Kong Keo, Krachak Chhrouk, Krachak Ses, Neang

Table 1. Submergence tolerance score of 351 rice germplasm. Cambodia, 1991.

Submergence tolerance score	Entries (n = 351)		Entries (n = 18,256) scored at IRRI (%)
	no.	%	
1	8	2.3	2
3	34	9.7	1
5	220	62.7	2
7	67	19.0	5
9	22	6.3	91

Table 2. Outstanding submergence-tolerant rice germplasm (submergence score 1) from Cambodia, 1991.

Accession no.	Cultivar	Province from which collected
1364	Angkear	Kampong Thom
1441	Damnoeub Sabai Bat	Steung Treng
1442	Damnoeub Ses	Svay Rieng
1446	Damnoeub Tong Sanke	Pur Sat
1464	Khngeng	Kampong Chhnang
1467	Khmang Romeang	Kampong Chhnang
1488	Kong Sar	Kampong Thom
1489	Kong Say	Pur Sat

Noy, Damnoeub Thnot, Kantourt Sa, Khpor Daung, Neang Noury, Neang Noy, Neang Rose, Neang Rovis, Neang San Kok, Sneng, Bantey Meas, Kantuy Damrei, Khneng Chnot, Clay, Dang Dav, Kong Soy, Neang Yi, Kong Bak Roteh, Sevith, Ansar Chang Kom, Khpor Daung,

Ang Kourt, Kaun Chen, Khmao, and Kaun Trai.

Cultivars scoring 1 and 3 would be useful for areas where fields are flood-prone at the early vegetative stage. They can also be used as donors for breeding submergence-tolerant rices. □

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Evaluation of indica/japonica crosses during boro season in West Bengal

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Indica/japonica crosses have reportedly performed well in areas where low temperature inhibits rice crop growth and yield. Boro (dry season) rice grown after lowland or deepwater rice in West Bengal experiences low temperature (10-15 °C) during early growth stages. Low temperature lengthens the crop duration, putting the reproductive phase into summer (Apr-May). High air temperature (35-40 °C) and premonsoon rain during this period occasionally damage boro rice.

Farmers grow short- to medium-duration, semidwarf modern varieties (MV) that average 4-5 t grain/ha. The congenial climate, however, makes it feasible to increase yields above the present level.

Nineteen indica/japonica advanced lines were obtained from IRRI and evaluated for seedling vigor, earliness, and high grain yield. Traditional, tall, boro variety CB1 and the promising, short-duration MV UPR103-80 were also evaluated in on-farm trials at Sonarhati village, Chinsurah, during 1990-91 boro. Minimum temperature between sowing and 45 d after sowing (DAS) was 10.8-11.1 °C. Cold tolerance, based on the amount of leaf yellowing, was recorded at 15, 30, and 45 DAS in the seedbed. IR8866-30-3-1-4-2, IR39739-7-4-3-1, and IR52418-B-B-B-6-2-1 were promising for cold tolerance and increased grain yield. IR8866-30-3-1-4-2 had the best average cold tolerance score (see table).

CB1 was tallest at 45 DAS followed by IR8866-30-3-1-4-2, which had the highest leaf number at 45 DAS. Indica/japonica lines yielded 13-15% more grain than UPR103-80. Grain type of indica/japonica crosses was comparable with that of CB1 and UPR103-80. Indica/japonica derivatives can possibly be used for varietal development programs in boro rice. □

Cold tolerance and grain yield in promising indica/japonica crosses. Chinsurah, West Bengal, 1990-91 boro season.

Entry	Type	Av cold tolerance (0-9 scale)	Seedling ht (cm) at 45 DAS	Leaves (no.) at 45 DAS	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)
IR8866-30-3-1-4-2	Indica/japonica	3.6	10.6	4.2	114	7.4
IR39739-7-4-3-1	Indica/japonica	4.0	9.0	3.2	116	8.0
IR52418-B-B-B-6-2-1	Indica/japonica	4.1	9.0	3.0	112	6.8
CB1	Tall indica	3.8	15.0	3.0	114	4.1
UPR103-80	Semidwarf indica	5.3	9.0	3.6	116	6.0
	Mean	4.2	10.5	3.4	114	6.6
	F value ^a	10.4**	41.3**	8.55**	10.5**	40.5**
	LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.5	1.4	0.6	0.6

^a*** = significant at the 1% level.